

STUDENTS' MOTIVATION IN THROUGH GAME IN LEARNING ENGLISH AT THE SECOND SEMESTER OF IAI AL MAWADDAH WARRAHMAH

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ABSTRAK

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengetahui semangat mahasiswa dalam mengikuti pembelajaran bahasa Inggris dengan menggunakan metode pembelajaran berbasis game. Subjek dalam penelitian ini adalah mahasiswa semester 2 IAI Al Mawaddah Warrahmah Kolaka. Teknik pengambilan data menggunakan metode observasi dengan instrument lembar observasi dengan beberapa indikator terkait motivasi siswa dalam mengikuti pembelajaran bahasa Inggris. Hasil penelitian ini menunjukkan bahwa pengajaran bahasa Inggris dengan menggunakan metode berbasis game dapat meningkatkan motivasi belajar mahasiswa semester 2 IAI Al Mawaddah Warrahmah dalam proses pembelajaran bahasa Inggris.

Kata Kunci: Pengajaran, Game dan Motivasi

INTRODUCTION

English becomes the most essential and very powerful language in the world. It is one of the international languages. Therefore, the role of English is required to face the era of globalization. Since English is treated as foreign and important language in Indonesia, it becomes one of the compulsory subjects taught in elementary schools, junior high school, senior high school and university level. As a result, the government always makes serious efforts to improve the quality of English teaching.

Harmer explains that learning English has to do with the four skills that have to be mastered by the students. The four skills are listening, speaking, reading and writing. Speaking and listening (oral skills) are said to relate to language expressed through the aural medium. Reading and writing are said to relate to language expressed through the visual medium (written symbol).¹ Another way of representing these skills is by reference not to the medium but to the activity of the language user. Therefore, speaking and writing are said to be active or productive skills, whereas listening and reading are said to be passive or receptive skills.

According to Gardner that motivation is a factor which comes from inside and outside motivation from internal side commonly that state the learners to gain particular object. The students' willingness to learn and their attitude, memory, intelligence and physical resources.² These factors have a great influence on teaching and learning process such as the teacher strategies, media in teaching, appropriate materials in the classroom situation.

Learning is the work that a teacher does in helping students to learn. Brown explains that teaching means showing or helping someone how to do something, giving instruction, guiding in the study of the something, providing with knowledge, causing to know or to understand.³ Teaching as an activity for guiding and facilitating the learners to learn and setting the condition of learning in the process of teaching and learning process.

¹ Jeremy Harmer. "How to Teach English an Introduction to the practice of English Language Teaching" the third Edition, London, 2001), p.198

²R.C. Gardner. *Social Psychology and Language Learning: The Role of Attitude and Motivation*. London: Edward Arnold.1985. p.25

³Brown. H. Douglas. *Principle of Language Learning and Teaching. Third Edition*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Inc.1994. p.10

Suhrah. 2019. Students' motivation...

Game is strategy to activate students in fun way. Teacher pushing, guiding and assessing ability of students thinking by game. Students are interested in game. They are happy in learning by game. Game make students are active during learning process because they are challenged to win the game. And also game is used to make students interested in following teaching-learning process. Teacher uses game to recall students' English skills. It is useful to keep students' English language skills in long memory.

In recent years, Game has been applied in the second semester of IAI AlMawaddah and from our own experience, it has shown its effectiveness in teaching and learning language. Game is an approach that helps students be more active in real life situations through the means of individual, pair and group work activities. It encourages students to practice the language they learn in meaningful ways. In classroom, playing vocabulary games is one of the activities which requires students to actively communicate with their classmates, using their own language. Thus the question we began to examine is, "Do games motivate students learn English effectively and if so, how?"

1. Literature review

Teaching is the work that a teacher does in helping students to learn. Brown explained that teaching theory some characteristic are: a) the experiences which most effectively implant in the individual a predisposition toward learning; b) the ways in the which a body of knowledge should be structured so that it can be most readily grasped by the learner, c) the most effective sequences in which to present to materials to be learned; and d) the nature and pacing of towards and punishments in the process of learning and teaching. Language teaching is complex activity in the teaching learning process.⁴

According to Oxford teaching strategies are behaviors or actions which learners use to make teaching more successful, self directed and enjoyable. In addition, Weinstein and Mayer state in Ellis: 531 that learning strategies are the behavior and thought that a learner engages in during learning that are intended to influence the learner's encoding process. By combining the definition above, language learning strategies are activities consciously chosen by learners for the purpose of regulating and managing their own language learning.⁵

⁴*Ibid.*, p.42

⁵Ellis, R. 1994. *The study of second language acquisition*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, p. 123

Another statement stated by Oxford and Green that teaching strategies are important elements of a language program and are considered as essential; factors for successful in teaching English. Selecting appropriate strategies could enhance the students' performance of English Foreign Language.⁶ Therefore, it is clear that the choices of strategies used by EFL teacher to improve students' achievement.

Motivation is likely one of the main factors that can make the students understand that material. Motivation may give students' confidence and ability to comprehend the language. The ability of the students to understand the teaching English through strategies can be influenced by high motivation. Wu, Yen, L., & Marek, M. state that motivation can increase rapidly, given a positive stimulus, but ability improvement may take significant time and study.⁷ Thus teacher should be responsible for their students. The teacher can only encourage by creative strategies. Motivation comes from within each individual.⁸

Harmer divided motivation into extrinsic and intrinsic motivation.

- 1) Extrinsic motivation concerns factors that come from outside the classroom.
- 2) Intrinsic motivation is related to factors come from inside the classroom.

Furthermore, Harmer explained that there are two types of extrinsic motivation, namely integrative and instrumental motivation. Integrative motivation deals with learners' desire to integrate themselves to target language culture as the strong form and knowing as much as they can about the target language culture as the weakest form of such motivation. Instrumental motivation is resulted from learners' desire to use the target language instrumentally (i.e. to get a better job, position or status). In addition, Harmer assumed that intrinsic aspect plays a vital part in most students' success or failure as language learner. He also considers some factors, which may affect intrinsic motivation as follow:

- a) Physical Conditions. Physical conditions have a great effect on learning and can alter a students' motivation either positively or negatively. Overcrowded classroom can be excessively de-motivating. Teacher should presumably try to make their classrooms as pleasant as possible. Even where condition is bad it may be possible to improve the atmosphere with posters, students' work, or wall magazine on the wall.

⁶Oxford. L., 1990. *Language learning strategies: what every teacher should know*. Boston: Heinle & Heinle. p.531

⁷Wu, W.-C.V., Yen, L. L., & Marek, M. (2011). *Using Online EFL Interaction to Increase Confidence, Motivation and ability*. Educational Technology & Society, 14 (3), p.118-129

⁸Jeremy Harmer, *op cit*, p. 8-9

Suhrah. 2019. Students' motivation...

- b) Method. The method used by a teacher in teaching also has some effect on students' motivation. The method by which students are taught must have some effect on their motivation. If they find it deadly boring they will probably become de-motivated, whereas if they have confidence in the method they will find it motivating;
- c) The Teacher. Teacher's personality may have effect on students' motivation. Therefore, a teacher needs to do everything possible to create a good rapport with the students. Whether the students like the teacher or not may not be very significant. What can be said, though, is that two teachers using the same method can have vastly different result;
- d) Success. Success or failure may affect students' motivation. It will be the teacher's job to set goals and tasks which most of his/her students can achieve. Success plays a vital part in the motivation of a student. Both complete successes may be de-motivating. It will be the teacher's job to set goals and tasks, at which he or she could realistically expect the students to be able to achieve. Many of the teacher's work in the classroom concerns getting of the level of challenge right.⁹

When teacher uses various strategies in teaching, it may raise students' interest in learning, especially in teaching English. Simon indicated that motivation which comes from themselves which is called intrinsic motivation is really important for gaining the better achievement in leaning. Intrinsically motivate students in learning process because they find them enjoyable and interesting with the teacher's strategies in teaching learning process.¹⁰

Language games are highly motivating. Enjoyment, excitement and passion are naturally generated from playing game. As AdamIndicates, game are self motivating to stimulate learners' interest and curiosity, which benefits learners best to play with the language in their first stages of language learning. With a law affective filtergame-like activities are meaningful and playful, thus they motivate children to learn, arouse their interest, and develop positive attitudes towards language learning. Such classroom activities are particularly suitable for primary school pupils who like to play games. When pupils are enjoying playing games, at the same time, they are learning language unconsciously.¹¹

Harmer holds that games are highly appreciated thanks to their amusement and interest. Teachers can use games to help their students practice more their skills of

⁹*Ibid.*, p.4

¹⁰Simon A.Lei. *Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation: Evaluating Benefits And Drawbacks from College Instructors' Perspective*. Journal Of Instructional Psychology, 2008. 37 (2). 153-160

¹¹*Ob cid.*, p.8

communication.¹² Games are proposed to solve the problem. Games bring in relaxation and fun for students, and they will learn and retain new words easily. Piller and Skilling Said that Games create the motivation for learners of English because of the competition between students. Vocabulary games bring real world context into the classroom, and enhance students' use of English in a flexible, communicative way.¹³

The advantages of using games are games play the important part of children's development and learning language. Gardner Instructional games can make the varieties of learners' benefits which range from cognitive aspects of language learning to the cooperative group dynamics. Learning language through games is useful, meaningful, worthwhile and effective that causes the motivation, relaxation and fun to learners in class.¹⁴ The learners can learn languages fundamentally and easily through games). Moreover, positive feedbacks from instructors or learners can improve learning better by learners' participating within a group or class. These motivate them to the succeeded goal. In addition, word games can reflect the learners themselves in their classroom and teachers can assess teaching process by themselves through word games as well.¹⁵

2. Method

To assess the motivation of learning English through games in the classroom, we want to know how students' experiences help with their learning and what progress they gain. Specifically, can we apply games as an effective means to make students feel more comfortable and interested in learning the English subject, which, in the second semester IAI Al Mawaddah Warramah, is usually believed to be boring rather than enjoyable?.

To achieve our goal, we focused on the perception and attitudes of our students as well as what students gained through their learning with English games. The plan involved conducting different kinds of games in our lessons so that we could see how students reacted to this method of learning English. We also wanted to find if there were any problems that occurred during the process of teaching. We also conducted a small post-class survey to elicit student's feelings and their own experiences in learning English. A simple

¹² Ibid., 5

¹³ Piller and Skilling. 2005. *English Language Teaching Strategies used by Primary Teachers In One New Delhi India School*. Accessed on 29 September 2014.

¹⁴ Alemi, Minoo (2010). Educational Games as a Vehicle to Teaching Vocabulary. *MJAL*, 425-438. Retrieved from <http://mjal.org/Journal/Educational%20Games%20as%20a%20Vehicle%20to%20Teaching%20Vocabulary.pdf>.

¹⁵ R.C. Gardner. 1985. *Social Psychology and Language Learning: The Role of Attitude and Motivation*. London: Edward Arnold.

Suhrah. 2019. Students' motivation...

questionnaire was designed beforehand to help students understand clearly the purpose of the survey. Furthermore, experienced teachers also helped us work out different ways of conducting effective vocabulary games by their lesson plans, handouts for games and their helpful advice. Further triangulation involved interviewing a student who had conducted similar research one year prior

3. Result

The second semester of IAI AL Mawaddah affective reaction to teacher's game. The students of second semester in this study showed different types of affective reactions toward teacher's game they received from their teacher during one semester. The result of students affective reactions to their teacher's game showed reasonable range of responses varying from positive affective. The result obtained from data analysis show that the students responded affectively for teacher's game. The students participant expressed that they thought carefully about the teacher's game. They also indicate that they get motivating from their teacher after getting study from their teacher which meant that they paid attention to teacher's game.

In another positive affective reaction was the students second semester liked teacher's game:

Researcher

Do you like the teacher's game?

Ita : yes I do

Researcher and you Rini?

So do you like all strategies of teacher and agree with them?

Rini : yes I like my teacher's game.

In another interview with Novita the second semester of student Al Mawaddah. She indicated that she like study when the teacher use game. And also Rini gave the same argument.

The positive affective reaction to teacher's game the students was being enjoy and happy. The students expressed their happiness when their teacher applied game in teaching. The students affective motivation to teacher's game in this study also include both students acceptance and rejection of their teacher's game.

Researcher

For this situation do you get spirit?

Ery: yes I get spirit when the teacher used game.

The student participants in this study reported their teacher's game were useful because they helped them to understand the material. Another reason was that their teacher's game helped them to avoid the mistakes they did in their assignment. The last reason the students gave on the usefulness of their teacher's game was that their teacher's game helped them to develop their English skill in general so that they can produce good future skill.

After collecting data by observing teachers' classes, interviewing students, and from our reflections of applying games in the classes we are teaching, we have come to some findings that will be helpful for teaching and learning English. The results will be displayed in two subsections, (i) students' expectations and motivation, (ii) students' progress.

A. Students' expectations and motivation

When being asked about the way of learning English, most students in our classes at the the second STAI AL MawaddahWarrahmah said they just joined English subject by teachers or looked up the teacher. Many of them did not attention their teacher. Some students only join in this class but they don't know teacher explanation. "It was so boring. I hated learning English!". Sometimes, students asked many questions regarding learning English like "Teacher, how can I understand the material and to remember this subject for a long time?", "How can I use English contexts?", "Can you tell me an easy and simple way to retain the English that I have learnt?". Frankel indicated that All of the learners expressed their wish to learn English effectively in more interesting ways than the traditional ways that they knew.¹⁶ What we wanted to know was whether English games worked or not.

Most of the learners (15 out of 20) were willing to join our games in groups and they tried their best to be the winners. The students especially liked such games as "Hangman" (guessing words that belong to the topic of jobs), animal squares (words puzzle) and advertisement poster competition (making an advertisement for a travel tour). Students collaborated quite actively in games that required group work, even the quiet students. They said that they liked the relaxed atmosphere, the competitiveness and the motivation that games brought to the classroom. Brown students have a chance to "use their imagination and creativity" during activities like games in the classroom; therefore they are motivated to

¹⁶Frankel, J.R.,&Wallen, N.E. *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education*. New York: McGraw-Hill. 2006. p. 74

Suhrah. 2019. Students' motivation...

learn.¹⁷ However, there were usually one or two students who seemed to isolate themselves from the activities. When asked to join their classmates, some students were reluctant to move from their seats to play games with their groups, some others just said they simply did not like to play the games. Nevertheless, 15 among 20 students expressed their satisfaction after the games and many of them wanted to play more as they said those games were fun and they found games helpful for their learning. In general, it was encouraging for us to know that most of our students showed pleasant feelings and positive attitudes towards learning English through games.

Moreover, we observed four lessons which applied games in providing and retaining students' English subject at the second semester IAI AL Mawaaddah Warrahmah. In different classes, we watched the game-like activity called "Selling and Buying Things (in which 10 students were shopkeepers selling fruits and food to the rest of the class. The shopkeepers had to sell all food they had and the shoppers had to buy all food they needed in the shortest time) in two different classes, and we observed the same students' reaction in both classes. Before the game started, the teachers tried to explain the game' rules to students and gave some examples. Once students understood the rules, they quickly rearranged their seats and grouped as instructed. The classes became as noisy as a real market. Students tried to use as many phrases and words they had learnt as possible. Thus, through this kind of activity students may be able to remember their English better. We had a second opportunity to observe a class again. This time, the teacher used a game called "Snakes and Ladders". Students worked in groups of five and everyone went from the start and tried to reach the finish as soon as possible by answering correctly to questions which were prepared by the teacher. After observing the game, we gave a small survey to 20 students with some questions about their feelings toward the game like; "Do you think this game is useful for you to remember words you have learnt?" and, "How can your classmates help you learn through the game?"... From this survey, we learnt that all 20 students agreed that games help them a lot in English learning. Among them, 12 students said that they could answer well two-thirds of questions in the game; and only one student could always respond to all questions.

¹⁷Brown, H. Douglas. 2001. *Teaching by Principle: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy* (2nd ed). New York: Addison Wesley Longman, Inc. P.163

B. Students' progress

Although our games were short activities and were applied to create a relaxed, pleasant learning atmosphere in the classrooms, we wanted games to be more than just fun. Games should also promote learning and teach students English as well. Therefore, it was important to know if our students made any progress in learning English through games. However, the action research was conducted in a limited time of two weeks, and it was hard to assess what our students had achieved because English learning is a cumulative process. However, students in our classes are gradually progressing in English subject and games help them to learn English that appear in the games and to recall their existing in English subject at the same time.

Generally, teachers can use the first part of a lesson, opening activity, for checking what students remember about the previous lesson or how many students understand of the topic. For example, the teacher at the second semester IAI AL MawaddahWarrahmah, conducted the game. In the same way, we chose the game "Hangman" with the topic of jobs to check students' memory of the English introduced in previous lessons. Our students got eleven correct answers out of twelve job cards which were passed out. Many students were really quick at answering and their answers were all accurate; others could not guess, but they could learn from their friends' answers.

Another example is the advertisement poster game. This is a game to check the students' understanding of the reading exercise about holiday and to see if students can understand of topic and structures to create a short piece of advertising for an interesting place. Students worked in four groups and all groups in the class produced quite nice, funny posters with short sentences using vocabulary of tourism and advertising. The classroom atmosphere was exciting as students discussed and chose the best poster of the class. In addition, our students revealed that games were very useful for them to enrich their vocabulary because they could learn from their classmates. Regarding the effectiveness of games, interviewed teachers reported that their students seemed to learn English more quickly and retain it better when it was applied in a relaxed and comfortable environment such as while playing games. In the same way, Laharini, student of the second IAI AL MawaddahWarrahmah that we interviewed also shared that she could understand more quickly and also for a long time when she learnt them through games. Through our post-game survey of one teacher's class, all students confirmed that their classmates helped them

Suhrah. 2019. Students' motivation...

understand the material for the games. Some students said they could learn English from their classmates. Also, some questioned students said that games are one of the most effective ways of learning English. Most students agreed that their use of learning English was becoming better since they actively joined games.

CONCLUSION

After presenting the findings, it is evident that using games may promote student's motivation. Game has become a term for curriculum design, method development and practice implementation of English language in the second IAI Al Mawaddah Warrahmah. It suggested that the teacher make good use of the advantage of game to create in teaching English supportive and learned-centered learning environment beneficial to equip students with much exposure to target learning. It also suggested that the educational authorities should be ready to access the strengths and weaknesses of our education system, and modify and prepare their knowledge to do their assignment. It is hoped that the students always spirit to join in English class.

According to the research results of the present study, the grounded theory is that students' motivation using game can be raised in English learning. In addition, game playing is an effective means to promote student's motivation because it helps students to learn by acting or recognizing objects in a natural way.

In conclusion, learning English through games is one effective and interesting way that can be applied in any classrooms. The results of this research suggest that games are used not only for mere fun, but more importantly, for the useful practice and review of language lessons, thus leading toward the goal of improving learners' communicative competence.

References

- Anyaeibu, Ruphina, Ting, Wei and Li, YI. (2012). Serious game motivation in an EFL classroom in Chinese primary school. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 17(1), 154-164. Retrieved from <http://www.tojet.net/volumes/v11i1.pdf#page=164>.
- Alemi, Minoos (2010). Educational Games as a Vehicle to Teaching Vocabulary. *MJAL*, 425-438. Retrieved from <http://mjal.org/Journal/Educational%20Games%20as%20a%20Vehicle%20to%20Teaching%20Vocabulary.pdf>.
- Brown, H. Douglas. 2001. *Teaching by Principle: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy (2nd ed)*. New York: Addison Wesley Longman, Inc.

- Ellis, R. 1994. *The study of second language acquisition*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Frankel, J.R., & Wallen, N.E. 2006. *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education*. New York: McGraw-Hill
- Harmer, Jeremy. 1992. *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. New York: Longman Published
- _____. 2001. *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. Third Edition. London
- Huyen, Nguyen Thi Thanh & Nga, Khuat Thi Thu (2003). Learning vocabulary through games, the effectiveness of learning vocabulary through games. *Asean EFL Journal*. Retrieved from http://www.asian-efl-journal.com/dec_03_sub.Vn.php.
- Oxford, L., 1990. *Language learning strategies: what every teacher should know*. Boston: Heinle & Heinle.
- Piller and Skilling. 2005. *English Language Teaching Strategies used by Primary Teachers In One New Delhi India School*. Accessed on 29 September 2014.
- R.C. Gardner. 1985. *Social Psychology and Language Learning: The Role of Attitude and Motivation*. London: Edward Arnold.
- Rubin, J., 1987. Learner Strategies: Theoretical Assumptions, Research History and Typology. In A. Wenden, and J. Rubin, eds. *Learner Strategies in Language Learning*. NY: Prentice-Hall International.
- Simon A. Lei (2008). *Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation: Evaluating Benefits And Drawbacks from College Instructors' Perspective*. *Journal Of Instructional Psychology*, 37 (2). 153-160
- Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL)* retrieved from <http://homework.wtuc.edu.tw/sill.php> (May 5, 2009) Downloaded on January 21 th, 2015
- Wu, W.-C.V., Yen, L. L., & Marek, M. (2011). Using Online EFL Interaction to Increase Confidence, Motivation and ability. *Educational Technology & Society*, 14 (3), 118-129